

A new era of monitoring research

FACTSHEET FOR FUNDERS, POLICY MAKERS & RESEARCH PERFORMING ORGANISATIONS

What is it?

OpenAIRE MONITOR (<https://monitor.openaire.eu/>) is an on-demand service providing tailored dashboards to Funders, Research Institutions, and Research Initiatives.

It streamlines the tracking and assessment of an organisation's research impact, fostering transparency and empowering informed decision-making.

Why?

Maximising research potential with actionable insights

In a rapidly evolving research landscape, organisations strive to understand their impact pathways, make informed decisions, and maximise their performance and societal contributions.

OpenAIRE MONITOR offers valuable insights, empowering organisations to strategically position themselves.

Distinctive Features of OpenAIRE MONITOR

Relevance for the community

- Co-develop indicators that make sense to all
- It's all about open science and open data
- Inclusiveness, transparency and replicability

Comprehensive coverage via the OpenAIRE Graph

- Beyond publications: Research Data, Software, Other Research Products
- Linked science
- Seamless integration with EOSC Infrastructure
- Fully embedded, from content providers to metrics

How? Methodological approach in a nutshell

Openness and transparency: Methodological assumptions are openly and clearly presented.

Coverage and accuracy: Based on data from multiple data sources to triangulate to the fullest extent possible, and provide meaningful indicators.

Clarity and replicability: Detailed construction methodology, so that it can be verified and used by the scholarly communication community to create ongoing updates to proposed statistics and indicators.

Readiness and timeliness: Built around well-established open databases and already tested knowledge extraction technologies - natural language processing (NLP) / machine-learning (ML) - using operational workflows in OpenAIRE to warrant timely results.

Trust and robustness: Strive to be reliable, robust, and aligned to other assessment methods so that it can be operationalised, used and reused, in conjunction with them.

Building your dashboard

It's about open data and collaboration

The process of building your dashboard

OpenAIRE MONITOR operates under **Open Science** principles, ensuring full transparency through the use of open data, open APIs, and a well-documented methodology. We begin by leveraging the **OpenAIRE Graph**, an extensive collection of linked scholarly information from open initiatives around the world, serving as the foundation for our indicators. Working closely with the **community**, our **data science experts** craft these indicators to ensure good coverage and granularity, customising them for diverse organisations.

Following this, we pair you with a dedicated expert, and with the support of a powerful infrastructure, we collaborate to tailor the dashboard to your needs and ensure the highest data quality. This results in a **unique dashboard**, optimised for analysis, reporting, and storytelling, which can be easily shared with your team or the wider public.

Indicators

Our **indicator themes** encompass a wide range of aspects, designed specifically for **tracking research activities and their impact**, evaluating the uptake of open science, collaborations, and more. Within each theme, we offer **multiple indicators and metrics**, allowing you to explore **trends and gain valuable insights**. These indicators can be analysed and compared across different dimensions of interest, such as fields of science, organisations, countries and data sources, enabling meaningful comparisons and contextual understanding.

About OpenAIRE

www.openaire.eu

Shifting scholarly communication towards openness and transparency and facilitate innovative ways to communicate and monitor research.

For more information, please contact:

info@openaire.eu

Additional guidance:

www.openaire.eu/guides

Useful Links for MONITOR

MONITOR Homepage

<https://monitor.openaire.eu>

Guides

Why OpenAIRE MONITOR

www.openaire.eu/monitoring-guide

How to join OpenAIRE

www.openaire.eu/funders-how-to-join-guide

This factsheet is also available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8136347>